

INTERESTING PROBLEMS OF TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

ZARNIGOR ZOIROVA

Fergana state university

Foreign languages faculty student of

20.120 group

Annotatsiya : Ushbu maqolada o'zbek tilining davlat tili sifatidagi nufuzi va mavqei tubdan oshirish maqsadida bajarilayotgan ishlar haqida fikr yuritilgan . Davlat tilining boyligi , sofligi uchun kurash doimo asosiy maqsad bo'lib kelganligi tasdiqlangan . Talabalar tomonidan hujjat turlariga namunalar yozilganda uchratadigan kamchiliklar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari ko'rsatilgan .

Tayanch so'zlar : davlat tili , rasmiy ish qog'ozlar uslubi , ma'naviyat , imlo qoidalar , yozma nutq , uslublar , til meyorlari , nutqning sofligi , hujjat turlari , nutq uslublari , nutqning boyligi .

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается работа, проводимая с целью коренного повышения престижа и положения узбекского языка как государственного. Подтверждено, что борьба за богатство и чистоту государственного языка всегда была главной целью. Показаны недостатки, с которыми столкнулись студенты при написании образцов видов документов и пути их устранения.

Ключевые слова: государственный язык, стиль официальных рабочих документов, духовность, орфографические правила, письменная речь, стили, языковые нормы, чистота речи, виды документов, стили речи, богатство речи.

Annotation: This article discusses the work being done in order to fundamentally increase the prestige and position of the Uzbek language as a state language. It has been confirmed that the struggle for the richness and purity of the state language has always been the main goal. Deficiencies encountered by students when writing samples of document types and ways to eliminate them are shown.

Key words: state language, style of official working papers, spirituality, spelling rules, written speech, styles, language norms, purity of speech, types of documents, speech styles, richness of speech.

The Uzbek language is one of the oldest and richest languages in the world, it is the spiritual wealth of our people. The state of Uzbekistan and the Uzbek nation have taken their rightful place in the world community, which is a proof that its national language has been formed and the foundations of statehood have been properly defined. Language is a part of the culture of any nation. People's speech is related to the fate of language. Therefore, we can say that the struggle for the development of the language and its simplicity is, first of all, the development of the nation and the new stage of Uzbekistan's development - the period when national and spiritual talents have been recruited. Among these are the wide-ranging works carried out to increase the prestige and reputation of the Uzbek language in society, the establishment of creative schools named after our famous writers, and the opening of the Alley of Writers. As A.Avloniy said, "To lose the national language is to lose the soul of the nation." Because the language is the main symbol of the nation's existence and unity, the mother tongue plays an important role in the spiritual maturity of a person and in the cultural and spiritual development of society. development is related to the development of society. Every member of our society, no matter what kind of specialist he is, must first of all learn and understand his mother tongue. A child who grows up with respect, love and respect for his mother tongue, is a success for his motherland, parents, and family. As the Honorable President III.Mirziyoyev said: "In order to inculcate our mother tongue in the hearts of the new generation, we must pay special attention to perfect teaching of the Uzbek language at all levels of education based on modern and innovative technologies. So that our children can speak Uzbek fluently, speak fluently and with a deeply smiling person let it be ". Ensuring the future, development, and prestige of the Uzbek language is our duty. In the last year, several important documents were adopted and practical work was carried out in our republic regarding the glorification, framing, and deeper study of our mother tongue and national literature. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally improve the status and position of the Uzbek language in the state language" was accepted (2019. 21.11. I105850 - COH).

October 21, when the Uzbek language was officially granted the status of the state language, is called "Uzbek language holiday". The Department of State Language Development was established within the structure of the Cabinet of Ministers. Implementation of control over compliance with laws on the state language by the department, introduction of public control in the field, development of the concept and State program for the development of the Uzbek language in 2020-2030; as well as improving the language policy. In the years of independence, since the mother tongue

literally became the state language, in the process of the state language, the work that should be carried out to fundamentally increase the status and status of the Uzbek language, departments of "Uzbek language and literature" were established in the region. It is necessary to dwell on the important aspects of the work on the increase of Uzbek language classes in the higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan, the introduction of new courses related to the field. It is important to accelerate the work on the Uzbek language based on the Latin structure and basic knowledge of the Uzbek language. It is important to teach students (who have studied at higher educational institutions of linguistics) the rules of spelling and specific aspects of the Arabic language. I think that the language should be learned in classes. The Arabic language is the defining factor of the literary language, because without it, the concept of a literary language loses its essence. Based on its social essence, the language improves along with the development of the society. Will continue to change and improve. It has been 25 years since the decision to make changes to the Latin-based Uzbek alphabet (06.05.1995). But the situation in this regard is still uncertain. In many cases, it is confused with the words of the Cyrillic alphabet, in particular, it is easy to make a mistake like by omitting vowels and consonants. The development of the state language, the identification of problems in the implementation of the state language should be addressed to every representative of this nation. First of all, documents of all organizations and enterprises must be written in the state language. This work should be approached with great responsibility and demand, in a necessary situation. The struggle for the status of the state language has always been one of the main issues. Not controlling the speech process, not taking a responsible approach to the language, using linguistic units that have reached the language culture, foreign words that have entered the diet, incorrect use of words, incorrect use of words and phrases cases are common. When students write samples of document types (application, explanatory letter, notice, biography, etc.), they can see flaws in their content:

1. Lack of perfect knowledge of Uzbek alphabet based on Latin script;
2. Tone of speech;
3. Adherence to literary language norms
4. Not understanding the difference between styles;

5. Failure to adhere to simplicity of speech;
6. Violation of the water order from a methodological point of view;
7. Violation of text logic;
8. Failure to take into account the grammatical and lexical aspects of the style of official working papers;
9. The fact that oral speech is the leader;
10. Failure to follow spelling rules.

The ways of elimination are as follows:

1. Complete mastery of spelling rules;
2. Work on oneself, constant control of one's oral and written speech;
3. Complete differentiation of speech styles;
4. To study the specific characteristics of document types;
5. Avoiding the use of conversational style;
6. Mastering the style of official working papers;

7. Mastering the specific aspects of written speech.

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